

DEVELOPING OF PUPILS' CREATIVE ABILITIES THROUGH MOTIVATIONAL EXERCISES

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Abstract. *This article discusses developing the creative activities of pupils through different kinds of motivational exercises in the educational process.*

Key words: *creativity, development of creative abilities, educational process, different creative methods, motivational exercises.*

РАЗВИТИЕ ТВОРЧЕСКИХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ УЧАЩИХСЯ ЧЕРЕЗ МОТИВАЦИОННЫЕ УПРАЖНЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается развитие творческих способностей младших школьников посредством различных видов мотивационных упражнений в образовательном процессе.*

Ключевые слова: *креативность, развитие творческих способностей, учебно-воспитательный процесс, различные творческие методы, мотивационные упражнения.*

INTRODUCTION

Creativity is an essential part of modern life, and it is something that should be fostered in children from a young age. From the fields of art and music, to engineering, science, business and education, creativity can be seen anywhere a mind endeavors to express itself and solves problems.

Contrary to popular belief, research has shown that creativity is not a predetermined trait and can be nurtured in any individual. Also, parents and teachers can play a key role in this by taking steps to preserve and enhance their children's and students' natural creativity at home.

Creating spaces that foster creativity and ignites the imagination will support activities that encourage creative thinking, such as painting with brushes, sculpting with play dough or clay, creating handcrafted items, building with blocks and conducting experiments, or listening to music and dressing up for theatrical play.

The development of those properties and abilities of the school pupil that are included in the concept of "creative abilities" is impossible in a short time. This is a goal-oriented work, a long process that occurs during training. It is important that creative activity is a permanent part of educational and extracurricular activities.

To implement the development of creative abilities, such methodological techniques as setting creative tasks, solving developmental problems, solving creative problems, use of visual aids, appeal to the life experience of pupils, asking questions and looking for in class answers are used. Getting knowledge independently, the pupil realizes himself as a creative person.

Encouraging creativity in children is of utmost importance for their holistic development and growth. Nourishing this skill in children during their formative years can have far-reaching effects on their growth and development. We can stimulate creativity by letting pupils express themselves through collage, painting, sculpture, sketching, writing, drama, art, the outdoors and STEM activities. By experimenting with different creative modes, they can build problem-solving skills that are useful in and out of the classroom.

MAIN PART

The methods of creativity chosen by the teacher when performing tasks characterize the corresponding levels of development of creative thinking, creative imagination. And the transition to a new level of development of creative abilities of pupils occurs in the process of accumulation of experience in creative activity by each pupil. If the teacher effectively uses the points in the prepared lesson plan, the lesson will give the result you expect. Well, the first thing I should mention is that how the method of motivation gives a hand students master the lesson, from methods that increase students' speech, and interest in classes. In the motivational part of your lesson plan, you will conduct such a short game or activity based on different kinds of methods such as the technology of SWOT, the diagram of VENN, Nilufar's flower, Four corners, Skeleton of fish, Case study, Brainstorming, Key terms, Assessment, Breakdown into clusters, ZUH mechanism (I know, I know, I want to know), Mixed up logical chains, reception "Marks in the margins", Compiling a sinewine, method of control questions, 3,4,5,6,7 methods and etc. Except for that there are a lot of methods of advanced pedagogical technologies. Visual, practical and also verbal methods are effectively used to progress creative abilities and qualities and therefore develop the individuality, the personality of each pupil who is in demand by society in their future activities. For example, the game method which is mostly used involves the use of various components of the game activity in combination with other techniques.

However teachers should take into consideration these methods depending on their age, psychological characteristics, and level of knowledge. Addition to this, these methods are related to the subject of the lesson, so that it attracts their attention and creates some interest or stimulus to learn the subject. It is very important that the duration of this stage is around 4-5 minutes and that it corresponds to the subject to be studied. Also, teachers use more poems, songs and games in the interest section of our lesson, it will arouse some interest in both pupils

and teachers. Poems are the most important role during the lesson. This is because the pupils memorise them, the words stay in their memory well, and songs help them to be correct their pronouncation as well as improve their speech.

There are given some requirements should be done teachers in the following lines:

Encourage questions: Give your kids the chance to explore and learn new things by encouraging them to ask questions about their surroundings. This can aid in the growth of their critical thinking abilities and lay the groundwork for their creative thinking.

Give your child the chance to learn by doing: Children learn best via hands-on experiences, so give them the chance to construct, experiment, and discover. They can increase their creative and problem-solving abilities as a result.

Encourage a growth mentality in your child: Motivate them to take on new challenges and teach them that failures are an opportunity for improvement. This may aid in their confidence-building and growth attitude development.

Encourage imaginative play: Playing with new concepts and opportunities is an important part of creative thinking, therefore encourage your child to do so.

Create opportunities for collaboration: Encourage your child to collaborate with others and give them chances to do so while they try to solve difficulties. This can foster their creativity and social skills development.

Reward Creativity: Another crucial step in developing children's creative thinking is to reward creativity. This can be accomplished by acknowledgment, appreciation, or even material compensation. Children are more likely to continue honing their creativity if their ingenuity is appreciated and rewarded.

Demonstrate Creative Thinking: Teaching youngsters how to think creatively is a terrific method to inspire them. This entails showcasing your creative and innovative problem-solving abilities. You are motivating people to follow suit by demonstrating how it is done.

Protect imagination by encouraging kids' natural curiosity. When their children reach that curious stage of development, which is characterized by a flood of questions, parents must resist the urge to become irritated and instead work to either provide the answers or aid in their search for them. Teaching youngsters how to find the answers on their own is much more beneficial.

Put a focus on creativity and reject the idea of "getting the correct answer." Rather than just correcting spelling mistakes or criticizing the accuracy of renderings, parents should encourage originality and inventive thinking in their children's writing and artwork.

While faults may be identified and corrected in youngsters, encouraging creativity is a far more complex and difficult task.

Encourage unconventional approaches to problem-solving. Give them options and let them use several channels to show what they've learned. Parents and instructors may foster their creative thinking by exposing kids to a variety of activities and themes. Vary activities with prompts in assignments, such as create, invent, discover, imagine if, and predict.

Fluency: Encourage students to unleash their imagination and freely generate as many ideas as possible without any constraints or limitations. The goal here is to encourage them to be open-minded and explore new and diverse concepts.

Flexibility: Teach students to embrace versatility in problem-solving by brainstorming multiple solutions, both technological and non-technological. This approach helps students to expand their problem-solving skills and increase their chances of finding effective solutions.

Originality: Foster divergent thinking skills by encouraging students to come up with unique and innovative ideas with broad implications. Encourage students to think outside the box and challenge traditional ways of thinking.

Elaboration: Emphasize the importance of enhancing ideas with vivid and exciting details. Encourage students to elevate their ideas to new heights and pay close attention to detail, as this can turn a mundane idea into a captivity. These demands are very important to develop pupil's creativity.

CONCLUSION

All in all, motivational exercise plays a role to develop pupil's creativity abilities.

Motivational exercises which is an important point in the development of abilities in children is the complexity, that is, the simultaneous improvement of several mutually complementary abilities. It is practically impossible to develop any one of the abilities without taking care of increasing the level of development of other abilities related to it. Skill as an organic part is included in the intellectual, interpersonal, many creative abilities, enriching them demand by society in their future activities.¹ Generally, it greatly helps pupils to think freely, use vocabulary, make meaningful sentences, and grow their worldviews in the motivation part of this lesson. It is the organization of high pupil activity during and after the lesson. Motivational exercises are the most important tool for building a student's self-confidence and help pupils shift their thinking to the topic they want to learn.

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Add to this, the lesson should be creatively organized. Because it affects to allow move into the system of reasoning and thinking necessary to achieve high success in the institution. As well as, motivational exercises are quick activities used at the beginning of the lesson. They are an effective way to help pupils creatively thought in the lesson and review material previously covered. In this way we, masters who is in the way of science should teach to use a lot of exercises as a motivation for pupils during the lesson. It helps to enhance creativity of pupils' not only in the lesson but also in their life's progress. These motivational exercises are included into the practical and mental given actions. Thus, in children it is necessary to form a positive motivation for learning, which implies the manifestation of strong-willed efforts in the process of mastering knowledge, which is the development of the creative abilities of school children².

Thus, it should be used as a special rule by each professional teacher in any lesson and, it brings to progress step by step in educational system. Even these requirements have a special goal in the educational process such as encourage questions. In this way pupils can develop critical thinking abilities and creative thinking through using the motivational exercises. Also, the development of pupils' creative abilities is an important problem of our time, especially given the condition for the introduction of the educational process.

Motivated pupils are much more likely to achieve their potential and find success.

Motivation is an essential ingredient in effective teaching and learning. It not only yields more positive behaviour in students, but it also contributes to a greater sense of wellbeing.

Understanding how to motivate children and young people in education is crucial, if we are to provide them with the best possible start in life.

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